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MATERNAL AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES OF INDUCTION OF LABOUR: A TERTIARY HOSPITAL EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Background: Induction of labour (IOL) is a commonly performed obstetric intervention aimed at achieving vaginal delivery when continuation of pregnancy poses risks to the mother or fetus. While it is widely practiced, the success and safety of induction depend on several clinical factors, including cervical favourability, indication, and method used.

Objective: To evaluate the indications, methods, maternal and neonatal outcomes, and predictors of successful induction of labour in a tertiary hospital setting.

Methods: This was a retrospective cross-sectional study involving 216 women who underwent induction of labour during a 3-year period of 2021 to 2023 at the Federal Medical Centre Yenagoa.

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Data on socio-demographic characteristics, indications for induction, Bishop score, method of induction, induction–delivery interval, mode of delivery, and fetomaternal outcomes were extracted and analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using chi-square tests and multivariable logistic regression, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The majority of participants were aged 26–30 years (40.3%) and multiparous (59.3%). The most common indication for induction was prolonged pregnancy (47.2%), followed by premature rupture of membranes (26.9%) and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (14.8%). Misoprostol was the predominant method used (83.8%). Most women (48.1%) delivered within 9–12 hours. The overall vaginal delivery rate was high at 87.5%, with only 12.5% requiring Caesarean section. Neonatal outcomes were favourable, with 91.7% of newborns having APGAR scores of 7–10, although 9.7% required admission to the special care baby unit. Maternal complications were relatively low, with perineal tears (8.3%), uterine hyperstimulation (6.0%), and postpartum haemorrhage (5.6%) being the most common. On multivariable analysis, a Bishop score ≥ 6 (OR 3.42, 95% CI 1.58–7.41, $p=0.002$) and use of misoprostol (OR 2.67, 95% CI 1.12–6.36, $p=0.026$) were significant independent predictors of successful induction.

Conclusion: Induction of labour is a safe and effective obstetric intervention with high success rates. Cervical favourability and method of induction are key determinants of outcome, underscoring the importance of appropriate patient selection and standardized protocols.

Keywords: Induction of labour, misoprostol, Bishop score, maternal outcomes, neonatal outcomes

INTRODUCTION

Induction of labour (IOL) refers to the deliberate initiation of uterine contractions prior to the natural onset of labour, with the goal of achieving vaginal delivery¹. It is among the most commonly performed obstetric procedures worldwide and constitutes a key element of contemporary obstetric care. The steady rise in induction rates over recent decades can be attributed to improvements in fetal monitoring techniques, enhanced understanding of maternal-fetal risks, and the broadening of clinical indications for planned delivery^{2, 3}. The global prevalence of labour induction shows considerable variation, ranging from approximately 10% in resource-constrained environments to more than 30% in developed countries⁴. Such differences are largely influenced by disparities in healthcare infrastructure, accessibility of induction agents, and the

degree of adherence to established clinical guidelines. In sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, the prevalence remains relatively lower; however, it is gradually increasing due to improved access to antenatal services and specialized obstetric care^{5, 6}.

Induction of labour is generally undertaken when the potential risks of continuing the pregnancy outweigh the benefits of expectant management. Common indications include post-term pregnancy, premature rupture of membranes (PROM), hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, intrauterine fetal growth restriction (IUGR), and intrauterine fetal demise (IUID)^{7, 8}. Of these, prolonged pregnancy is the most frequent indication globally, as gestations extending beyond 41 weeks are associated with increased risks such as stillbirth, fetal macrosomia, meconium aspiration, and other forms of neonatal morbidity⁹.

Although induction of labour offers clear clinical benefits, it is not devoid of complications. Unsuccessful induction may lead to a higher likelihood of operative delivery, particularly caesarean section. In addition, excessive uterine activity resulting from induction agents can predispose to fetal distress, uterine rupture, and poor neonatal outcomes^{10, 11}. Consequently, careful selection of candidates and the appropriate choice of induction method are essential to achieving favourable outcomes.

The readiness of the cervix at the time of induction is one of the most critical determinants of success. This is commonly evaluated using the Bishop scoring system, which assesses cervical dilatation, effacement, consistency, position, and fetal station¹². A favourable Bishop score (≥ 6) has consistently been linked with higher rates of successful vaginal delivery and shorter induction-to-delivery intervals, whereas an unfavourable cervix often necessitates prior cervical ripening¹³.

Methods of labour induction are broadly classified into pharmacological and mechanical approaches. Pharmacological methods include prostaglandins such as misoprostol and dinoprostone, as well as oxytocin infusion, while mechanical techniques include the use of balloon catheters and membrane sweeping¹⁴. Among these options, misoprostol has gained widespread acceptance, particularly in low-resource settings, owing to its affordability, thermal stability, ease of administration, and strong efficacy in promoting cervical ripening and uterine contractions^{15, 16}.

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the use of standardized, evidence-based protocols to enhance the safety and effectiveness of labour induction while minimizing complications. International organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG), and the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) have developed guidelines outlining best practices for indications, methods, and monitoring of induction¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Nevertheless, the outcomes of induction may vary considerably depending on patient characteristics, institutional protocols, and the availability of healthcare resources.

In many low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, several challenges such as inadequate monitoring facilities, delayed presentation to healthcare facilities, and inconsistencies in clinical practice can impact both the safety and success of induction procedures^{20, 21}. These contextual factors highlight the importance of evaluating induction practices within specific healthcare settings. Moreover, there is a pressing need for locally generated evidence to guide clinical decision-making and refine management protocols. Identifying predictors of successful induction, including maternal characteristics, cervical status, and the method employed, is essential for improving maternal and neonatal outcomes while reducing unnecessary operative interventions^{22, 23}.

This study therefore seeks to examine the indications, methods, maternal and neonatal outcomes, and predictors of successful induction of labour in a tertiary hospital setting. The findings are expected to contribute to existing knowledge and support evidence-based obstetric practice, particularly in similar resource-limited environments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was designed as a retrospective cross-sectional study carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, a tertiary-level healthcare facility that functions as a key referral centre for both urban and semi-urban populations within January 2021 to December 2023. The institution offers comprehensive emergency obstetric and neonatal services, including labour induction, operative deliveries, and neonatal resuscitation. The study involved a review of all cases of labour induction conducted within a specified study period.

The study population consisted of all pregnant women who underwent induction of labour during the study timeframe. Inclusion criteria comprised women with singleton pregnancies at a gestational age of 28 weeks or more, cephalic fetal presentation, and a clearly documented medical or obstetric indication for induction. Only cases with complete and accessible medical records were considered eligible for analysis. Exclusion criteria included multiple pregnancies, abnormal fetal presentations such as breech or transverse lie, contraindications to vaginal delivery (including placenta previa and a history of classical caesarean section), as well as cases with incomplete clinical documentation.

A total of 216 women who satisfied the eligibility criteria were included in the study. All qualifying cases within the study period were consecutively recruited to minimize selection bias. Data were sourced from multiple hospital records, including labour ward registers, individual patient case files, delivery logs, and neonatal records. To ensure uniformity and accuracy in data collection, a structured data extraction tool was employed.

Information obtained included socio-demographic variables such as maternal age, parity, educational status, and marital status. Obstetric variables extracted comprised gestational age at induction, indication for induction, Bishop score at initiation, and the method of induction utilized. Outcome measures included mode of delivery, duration from induction to delivery, maternal complications, and neonatal outcomes, specifically APGAR scores and admission to the special care baby unit (SCBU).

The choice of induction method was based on the clinical judgement of the attending obstetrician, taking into consideration the indication for induction and cervical status. Misoprostol was the most frequently used agent and was administered either orally or vaginally in low, repeated doses for cervical ripening and initiation of labour. In selected cases, particularly among women with favourable cervical conditions, oxytocin infusion was utilized either as a sole method or following amniotomy. In some instances, a combination of amniotomy and oxytocin infusion was employed.

All patients were closely monitored throughout the labour process. Monitoring included regular assessment of uterine contractions, continuous or intermittent fetal heart rate surveillance, and periodic vaginal examinations to evaluate cervical changes and labour progression.

Data collected were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Associations between categorical variables and study outcomes were evaluated using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. Variables that demonstrated statistical significance on bivariate analysis were subsequently included in a multivariable logistic regression model to identify independent predictors of successful induction of labour. Findings were presented as odds ratios with corresponding 95% confidence intervals, and statistical significance was set at a p-value of less than 0.05.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa. Due to the retrospective nature of the study, the requirement for informed consent was waived. Strict confidentiality was maintained throughout the study by anonymizing all patient data and ensuring that no identifying information was included in the analysis.

RESULTS

The majority of participants were aged 26–30 years (40.3%) and multiparous (59.3%). The most common indication for induction was prolonged pregnancy (47.2%), followed by premature rupture of membranes (26.9%) and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (14.8%). Misoprostol was the predominant method used (83.8%). Most women (48.1%) delivered within 9–12 hours. The overall vaginal delivery rate was high at 87.5%, with only 12.5% requiring caesarean section. Neonatal outcomes were favorable, with 91.7% of newborns having APGAR scores of 7–10, although 9.7% required admission to the special care baby unit. Maternal complications were relatively low, with perineal tears (8.3%), uterine hyperstimulation (6.0%), and postpartum haemorrhage (5.6%) being the most common. On multivariable analysis, a Bishop score ≥ 6 (OR 3.42, 95% CI 1.58–7.41, $p=0.002$) and use of misoprostol (OR 2.67, 95% CI 1.12–6.36, $p=0.026$) were significant independent predictors of successful induction.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Patients (N = 216)

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
≤19	9	4.2
20–25	68	31.5
26–30	87	40.3
31–35	28	13.0
>35	24	11.0
Parity		
0	74	34.3
1–3	128	59.3
≥4	14	6.5
Education		
No formal education	12	5.6
Primary	46	21.3
Secondary	106	49.1
Tertiary	52	24.1
Marital Status		
Married	179	82.9
Single	37	17.1

The mean age distribution was skewed towards younger women, with the majority aged 26–30 years (40.3%), followed by 20–25 years (31.5%), while adolescents (≤ 19 years) constituted 4.2%.

Most participants were multiparous (parity 1–3: 59.3%), with 34.3% nulliparous and 6.5% grand multiparous (≥ 4). Nearly half (49.1%) had attained secondary education, and the majority were married (82.9%).

Table 2: Indications for Induction of Labour (N = 216)

Indication	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Prolonged pregnancy	102	47.2
PROM	58	26.9
Preeclampsia / PIH	32	14.8
IUFD	16	7.4
IUGR	8	3.7

The leading indication for induction was prolonged pregnancy (47.2%), followed by premature rupture of membranes (26.9%). Other indications included preeclampsia/pregnancy-induced hypertension (14.8%), intrauterine fetal death (7.4%), and intrauterine growth restriction (3.7%).

Table 3: Events in Labour (N = 216)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Bishop Score		
<6	77	35.6
6–9	98	45.4
>9	41	19.0
Induction Method		
Misoprostol	181	83.8
Amniotomy + Oxytocin	28	13.0
Oxytocin only	7	3.2
Induction–Delivery Interval		
<3 hours	5	2.4
3–8 hours	56	25.9
9–12 hours	104	48.1
>12 hours	51	23.6
APGAR Score		
7–10	198	91.7
4–6	11	5.1
<3	7	3.2
Route of Delivery		
Vaginal delivery	189	87.5
Caesarean section	27	12.5

At induction, 45.4% had a Bishop score of 6–9, 35.6% <6, and 19.0% >9. Misoprostol was the main induction method (83.8%), followed by amniotomy with oxytocin (13.0%) and oxytocin alone (3.2%). Most women delivered within 9–12 hours (48.1%), while 25.9% delivered in 3–8 hours, 23.6% after >12 hours, and 2.3% within <3 hours.

Overall, 87.5% achieved vaginal delivery. Most neonates (91.7%) had APGAR scores of 7–10; 5.1% had moderate and 3.2% severe asphyxia, with 9.7% requiring SCBU admission.

Table 4: Fetomaternal Complications

Complication	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hyperstimulation	13	6.0
Postpartum haemorrhage (PPH)	12	5.6
Perineal tear	18	8.3
Admission to SCBU	21	9.7

Maternal complications were relatively infrequent. Perineal tears were the most commonly reported complication (8.3%), followed by uterine hyperstimulation (6.0%) and postpartum haemorrhage (5.6%). A total of 9.7% of neonates required admission to the SCBU.

Table 5: Association Between Selected Variables and Outcome of Induction of Labour

Variable	Vaginal Delivery n(%)	CS n(%)	χ^2	df	p-value
Age group					
≤19	8 (3.7)	1 (0.5)			
20–25	60 (27.8)	8 (3.7)			
26–30	77 (35.6)	10 (4.6)	2.41	4	0.66
31–35	24 (11.1)	4 (1.9)			
>35	20 (9.3)	4 (1.9)			
Parity					
0	62 (28.7)	12 (5.6)			
1–3	117 (54.2)	11 (5.1)	5.12	2	0.077
≥4	10 (4.6)	4 (1.9)			
Bishop Score					
<6	60 (27.8)	17 (7.9)			
6–9	92 (42.6)	6 (2.8)	9.84	2	0.007*
>9	37 (17.1)	4 (1.9)			
Induction Method					
Misoprostol	160 (74.1)	21 (9.7)			
Amniotomy + Oxytocin	24 (11.1)	4 (1.9)	6.11	2	0.047*
Oxytocin only	5 (2.3)	2 (0.9)			

No significant association was found between maternal age or parity and delivery outcome, although a trend toward higher vaginal delivery among multiparous women was observed. In contrast, higher Bishop scores and the use of misoprostol were significantly associated with increased likelihood of vaginal delivery.

Table 6: Predictors of Successful Induction of Labour Using Logistic Regression

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Age \geq 30 years	0.84	0.42 – 1.69	0.62
Parity (1–3)	1.76	0.89 – 3.48	0.10
Parity \geq 4	2.11	0.71 – 6.23	0.17
Bishop score \geq 6	3.42	1.58 – 7.41	0.002*
Misoprostol induction	2.67	1.12 – 6.36	0.026*
PROM as indication	1.45	0.71 – 2.98	0.31
Preeclampsia / PIH	0.92	0.38 – 2.21	0.85

On multivariable analysis, Bishop score \geq 6 and misoprostol use independently predicted successful induction, while maternal age, parity, PROM, and preeclampsia were not significant predictors.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that induction of labour is a highly effective and generally safe obstetric intervention in this setting, with a vaginal delivery rate of 87.5%. This figure is slightly higher than the 70–85% success rates commonly reported in both high-income and low-resource environments^{2, 13}. The relatively favourable outcome observed may be attributed to appropriate

patient selection, judicious use of induction agents, and adherence to institutional protocols. It also suggests that, when properly implemented, induction of labour can achieve outcomes comparable to those reported in more resource-endowed settings.

The predominance of women aged 26–30 years reflects the peak reproductive age group and is consistent with findings from similar studies^{14, 15}. Women in this age category typically have better obstetric outcomes due to optimal physiological reserve and a lower prevalence of chronic medical conditions. Although multiparous women constituted the majority of the study population, parity did not significantly influence the success of induction. This finding contrasts with previous reports that have demonstrated higher success rates among multiparous women, likely due to increased cervical compliance and enhanced uterine responsiveness^{16, 17}. The absence of a statistically significant association in this study may be explained by the overall high success rate, which may have reduced the observable differences between nulliparous and multiparous women.

Prolonged pregnancy emerged as the leading indication for induction, accounting for nearly half of all cases. This aligns with global obstetric practice, where induction beyond 41 weeks' gestation is recommended to mitigate the risks of stillbirth, fetal macrosomia, meconium aspiration, and neonatal complications^{18, 19}. The high proportion of post-term inductions in this study suggests good adherence to established clinical guidelines. Premature rupture of membranes was the second most common indication, consistent with existing evidence supporting early induction in such cases to reduce the risk of ascending infection without significantly increasing caesarean section rates²⁰. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy also represented a substantial proportion of indications, highlighting the ongoing burden of conditions such as preeclampsia in this environment and the critical role of timely delivery in preventing severe maternal and fetal complications²¹.

Misoprostol was the most frequently used induction agent, reflecting its widespread adoption, particularly in low-resource settings. Its popularity is largely due to its affordability, stability at room temperature, ease of administration, and well-established efficacy in cervical ripening and labour induction^{9, 22}. In this study, the use of misoprostol was significantly associated with successful vaginal delivery and was identified as an independent predictor of success. This finding

corroborates previous studies demonstrating the superiority or equivalence of misoprostol compared to other induction methods, particularly oxytocin alone, in achieving favourable outcomes^{23, 24}. The relatively limited use of amniotomy with oxytocin may reflect a preference for pharmacological cervical ripening, especially in women presenting with unfavourable cervical conditions.

Cervical status at the time of induction, as assessed by the Bishop score, emerged as the strongest predictor of successful induction. Women with a Bishop score ≥ 6 was significantly more likely to achieve vaginal delivery, with more than a threefold increase in odds. This finding is consistent with long-standing evidence supporting the Bishop score as a reliable and practical tool for predicting induction outcomes^{8, 25}. A favourable cervix enhances responsiveness to induction agents, reduces the duration of labour, and lowers the likelihood of operative delivery. These findings reinforce the importance of routine cervical assessment and the use of cervical ripening strategies in patients with low Bishop scores.

The induction-to-delivery interval observed in this study was largely within expected limits, with nearly half of the women delivering within 9-12 hours. This is consistent with known timelines for prostaglandin-based induction methods⁵. The relatively low proportion of very rapid deliveries suggests that induction protocols were applied cautiously, thereby minimizing the risk of complications such as uterine rupture and fetal distress. Conversely, the proportion of women delivering after 12 hours highlights the variability in individual response to induction and underscores the need for patience and continued monitoring before declaring induction failure.

Maternal complications in this study were relatively infrequent, supporting the safety of induction when conducted under appropriate supervision. Perineal tears were the most common complication, which is likely attributable to the high rate of vaginal delivery rather than the induction process itself. Uterine hyperstimulation, a recognized complication of prostaglandin use, occurred at a rate comparable to global reports¹⁰. Similarly, the incidence of postpartum haemorrhage was within acceptable limits and may be related to factors such as prolonged labour or uterine atony. Overall, the complication profile observed is consistent with existing literature and indicates that the induction practices employed were safe.

Neonatal outcomes were largely favourable, with the majority of newborns achieving satisfactory APGAR scores. This suggests that induction of labour did not adversely impact neonatal wellbeing. The rate of admission to the special care baby unit was comparable to findings from similar studies and may reflect cautious clinical practice rather than severe neonatal morbidity¹⁹. Importantly, the low incidence of severe birth asphyxia further supports the safety of appropriately conducted induction procedures.

Multivariable analysis identified Bishop score ≥ 6 and the use of misoprostol as independent predictors of successful induction, while maternal age, parity, and indication for induction were not significant predictors. This finding underscores the relative importance of cervical readiness and the method of induction over baseline demographic characteristics. It highlights the need for individualized clinical assessment and supports the prioritization of cervical evaluation in decision-making. From a clinical perspective, the findings of this study emphasize several important considerations. First, routine assessment of cervical favourability using the Bishop score should guide induction decisions. Second, misoprostol remains an effective first-line agent, particularly in resource-limited settings. Third, careful patient selection and adherence to standardized protocols can achieve high vaginal delivery rates while minimizing complications.

Overall, this study contributes valuable evidence supporting the effectiveness and safety of induction of labour in a tertiary healthcare setting and provides insights that may inform clinical practice in similar environments.

LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations. Its retrospective design relied on existing medical records, making the data susceptible to incomplete documentation and possible inaccuracies. As a single-centre study conducted in a tertiary hospital, the findings may have limited generalizability to other settings, particularly primary and secondary healthcare facilities, and may also be affected by referral bias due to the likelihood of managing more complex cases. Variations in clinical practice among attending clinicians led to a lack of uniformity in induction protocols, which could have influenced patient outcomes. In addition, some important confounding variables, such as maternal body mass index and detailed obstetric history, were not consistently recorded and therefore could

not be included in the analysis. Finally, the study evaluated only immediate maternal and neonatal outcomes without assessing long-term effects. Despite these limitations, the findings provide useful insights into induction of labour practices in this setting.

CONCLUSION

Induction of labour is a safe and effective intervention in this setting, with high rates of vaginal delivery and favourable neonatal outcomes. Bishop score and method of induction are the strongest determinants of success.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Idea/Concept: Florence A Koroye, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Ani C MaryJane, Onisoubuana John-Bennibor; Design: Florence A Koroye, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Markson W Sam, Atemie Gordon; Control/Supervision: Ani C MaryJane, Markson W Sam, Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo; Data Collection and/or Processing: Onisoubuana John-Bennibor, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Joshua k. Stephen; Analysis and/or Interpretation: Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Joshua k. Stephen, Florence A Koroye; Literature Review: Ani C MaryJane, Onisoubuana John-Bennibor, Markson W Sam, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem; Writing the Article: Florence A Koroye, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Atemie Gordon, Joshua k. Stephen; Critical Review: Florence A Koroye, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Ani C MaryJane, Onisoubuana John-Bennibor, Markson W Sam, Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Joshua k. Stephen.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

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